
EMPLOYEE TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT AS A MODEL FOR ORGANIZATIONAL SUCCESS

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Abstract:

This article reviewed employee training and development as a model for organizational performance and effectiveness. The various literatures reviewed on the topic in question showed that, training and development had positively correlated and claimed statistical significant relationship with employee performance and effectiveness and can advance organizational growth and success. In order to improve employee training and development as well as improved performance and service delivery, it is recommended that management should increase the number of employees taking part in training and development.

Keywords: *Employee; Training; Development; Performance; Organizational; Success.*

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1. Introduction

Training and development is an important activity that increases the performance of employee in an organization and is a building block which enhances the growth and success of an organization. Armstrong (2009) stated that organizations could benefit from training and development through winning the "heart and minds of" their employees to get them to identify with the organization, to exert themselves more on its behalf and to remain with the organization. Training and development are the processes of investing in people so that they are equipped to perform well and are part of an overall human resource management approach that hopefully will result in people being motivated to perform (McDowall & Saunders 2010). The following key terms are defined for better elaboration.

Training

This activity is both focused upon, and evaluated against, the job that an individual currently holds; training refers to bridging the gap between the current performance and the standard desired performance (Garavan, 1997).

Development

This activity focuses upon the activities that the organization employing the individual, or that the individual is part of, may partake in the future, and is almost impossible to evaluate.

Antonacopoulou (2000), defined development as the capacity and capability building on an employee and thus as of whole organization, to meet the standard performance level.

Training and Development

This can be described as "an educational process that involves the sharpening of skills, concepts, changing of attitude and gaining of more knowledge to enhance the performance of employees". Human resource management regards training and development as a function concerned with organizational activity aimed at bettering the job performance of individuals and groups in organizational settings. It is an attempt to improve current or future employee performance by increasing an employee's ability to perform through learning, usually by changing the employee's attitude or increasing his or her skills and knowledge." Employee performance depends on many factors like job satisfaction, knowledge and management but there is relationship between training and performance (Chris, 2010). This shows that employee performance is important for the performance of the organization and training and development is beneficial for the employee to improve.

Despite great roles of training and development in organizational growth and success, many organizations lack basic skills that will encourage the growth and success of their organization by training and developing of employee. According to Chiaburu & Teklab (2005), job training and development is a complicated matter and has been the focus of much of the training literature.

This study therefore reviewed relevant articles on the impact of training and development as a model for organizational growth and development.

2. Theories on Training and Development

Cole (2002), defined training as a learning activity directed towards the acquisition of specific knowledge and skills for the purpose of an occupation or task. The focus of training is the job or task for example, the need to have efficiency and safety in the operation of particular machines or equipment, or the need for an effective sales force to mention but a few. According to Garavan (1997) and Berge *et al.* (2002) training is the planned and systematic modification of behavior through learning events, activities and programs which results in the participants achieving the levels of knowledge, skills, competencies and abilities to carry out their work effectively. Chris (2010), asserted that employee performance depends on many factors like job satisfaction, knowledge and management but there is relationship between training and performance indicating that employee performance is important for the performance of the organization in which training & and development is beneficial for the employee to improve training performance.

If employees are to experience flexibility and effectiveness on the job, they need to acquire and develop knowledge and skills, and if they are to believe that they are valued by the organization they work for, then they need to see visible signs of management's commitment to their training and career needs (McDowall and Saunders, 2010). To enhance job performance, training skills and behaviours have to be transferred to the workplace, maintained over time, and generalized across contexts (Holton & Baldwin, 2000).

Most employers consider employee training as a costly and unimportant expense to their companies. Job satisfaction is a pleasurable or state of positive emotion resulting from a positive appraisal of the job or job experiences (Locke, 1976). Tsai, *et al.*, (2007), suggests that commitment results from adequate training and development for successful job completion and an increase in job performance.

The latter have their uses, but I always urge people to think of work-based action first.” This is not the case because there are many benefits accrued to both the organization and the individual employee with this venture. Impacting your workers with the skills necessary to get the job done will boost their job morale and fewer mistakes will be made. Untrained personnel may be more costly than even the wages paid to them due to the mistakes they could easily make.

Braga (1995), affirms that training delivery style is a very important part of training and development and also found 59.0% of respondents cited demonstration or onsite coaching the most frequent method of training facilitation techniques. This find was in line with Braga found most of the research participants reported they were attended on job (demonstration) training, which help to transform it into practice.

Knowing that they are cared about investing in, employees will tend to work harder in order to reciprocate the favour. Hard work eventually leads to more returns, and this might be in terms of production or even profit margins. Trained personnel will also ask for less help, ultimately improving their own efficiency further. Employee training and development gives the workforce a good chance to realize their potential and eventually work at their highest level. When an employer realizes the potential in a staff member, and then sends that employee to class to improve his or her skills, the trained staff will be more willing to work at their best level of ability. Maximizing the potential of the workforce has a direct positive impact on the business or organization’s profit levels. A trained employee can handle more responsibilities than before due to their newly acquired know-how, which in-turn, improves their versatility. Proficiency in a particular area might even reduce chances of equipment breakdowns as a result of human error, and therefore also reduce the cost of repairs.

Imparting skills to employees is also another tactic of retaining your skilled workforce. A workforce that has been trained by the company will feel as part of the company family. They will feel happier in their jobs and valued by their employer, and therefore will be more likely to stay within the firm. A trained staff will develop a sense of self-worth and dignity as they will view themselves as more valuable to the organization, which will eventually culminate in higher job satisfaction. The retention of trained staff will not only reduce the high cost of recruiting new staff but also have a positive impact on production.

The business industry is very competitive and this is partly due to the advancements in technology. To remain in fair competition in the market, a firm needs to have skilled and trained workers who are familiar with both the changes in technology and the changing tastes of the consumers. Training personnel in these new areas will improve the company’s strength in market presence.

Employee training and development is essential for every organization's success as it ensure that skills, abilities and knowledge levels of the employee are being According to Blain (2009), research shows that 44% of employees receive job-related technical skills training and 33% receive information technology (IT) skills training. 18% of employees have undertaken sales related training in the past year, while 25% have undertaken personnel development skills training, 21% management skills training and 15% leadership skills development.

Training and development activities in which employees had participated bring new potentials of employees in performing task and resulted in employee effectiveness. The finding was in line with the principles of Cole (2002) suggestion on purpose of facilitating training as it was to create a learning media directed towards the acquisition of specific knowledge and skills for the purpose of an occupation or task. There are a variety of reasons for employee training and development, including (but not limited to):

- On boarding new hires
- Individual employee development plans, where you are training to fill a skill or knowledge gap, address a performance issue, or prepare the employee to take on greater managerial and/or leadership responsibilities
- Succession planning, where you have identified high-potentials and are grooming the next generation of leaders
- Addressing technology changes and providing the skills and knowledge needed to leverage new and emerging technologies
- Addressing legal and/or regulatory issues and changes
- Helping your team address a range of issues and opportunities around growth and change, including helping the team and organization respond and adapt to structural change in the economy.

Organizations should develop a solid organizational training and development plan that includes a selection of public, open-enrolment, programs of choice for employees' individual learning needs and custom in-house training for team training and development needs.

2.1. Rationale for Training and Development

Staff training is an element in raising morale because it sounds out people for possible future promotions. It is important to train and develop each employee so far as possible even if that means running the risk of losing them to other organizations. This growing awareness of the importance of training and development over the past decades is also supported by reports that employees were spending more in aggregate terms on these activities.

Technological developments and organizational change have gradually caused some employers to realize that success lie in the skills and abilities of their employees thus this means considerable and continuous investment in training and development. This has been brought to light by the rise in human resources management, with its emphasis on the importance of people and the skills they possess in enhancing organizational efficiency. Such human resource management concepts such as "commitment" to the company and the growth in the "quality" movement have promoted senior management teams to realize the increased importance of training, employee development and long term education intended to mean basic instruction in

knowledge and skills designed to enable people to make the most of life in general. There has also been increased recognition of the need to complement the qualities of employees with the needs of the organization. Such concepts require not only careful planning but also greater emphasis on employee development.

2.2. Communication and Proficiency

Cheng and Ho (2001) indicate that adequate training and development produces marked improvements in employee communication and proficiency of performances as well as extending retention time. Moreover, when programs target communication skills with coworkers, there are significant increases in profit as well as a greater number of reported positive working relationships that are formed. Employees with good communication skills gather more information concerning procedures and technologies related to job performances, thus assuming greater accountability and subsequent responsibility, both of which effect improve proficiency (Adams, 1989; Gordon, 1977). Also, training and education have been shown to have a significant positive effect on job involvement, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment (Karia & Asaari, 2006).

2.3. Attitudes in Training on Attitude

According to Ahmad and Karia (n.d.), the relationship between training and attitude as it relates to working with others. Employees with positive attitudes become stakeholders in the process and job accomplishment is of a higher priority. Furthermore, successful organizations achieve a partnership between workers and management. The partnership includes participation in teamwork activities and continuous learning application. The reported findings further suggest that an employee's participation in decision making and problem solving develops organizational trust (Anschutz, 1995).

2.4. Employee Capacity Building as Model for Organizational

Learning, training and development can have two meanings for the employees. It can be perceived as an intrinsic motivator, as they support employees' growth, learning and development. It can also be an extrinsic motivator, because they give employees more tools they can use during their work for achieving their goals (Bakker and Leiter, 2010). Moreover, in the survey conducted by Paradise (2008), employees ranked quality of workplace learning opportunities as the first factor influencing their engagement, therefore management of organizations should help employees updating their experience and increasing their knowledge and skills through giving appropriate trainings. Generally it is understood that when employees get to know more about their job, their confidence increases there by being able to work without much supervision from their immediate managers which in turn builds their self-efficacy and commitment.

3. Benefits of Training and Development

Some of the key benefits for organizations that make employee training and development a priority as suggested by *Antunka, Napoleon* include the following:

3.1. Increased Productivity

Timely and relevant training helps boost productivity. By closing skills, knowledge and performance gaps, and arming your employees with new ideas, best practices and skills that they can put into practice in their jobs right away, their competence, ability and confidence levels increase. As a result, these employees are able to make better decisions, and do their jobs smarter and more efficiently.

3.2. Return on Investment (ROI)

By making training and development a strategic priority of the organization, and implementing it in a thoughtful and deliberate manner, a company can benefit from measurable ROI. You can measure for impact, for qualitative and quantitative ROI, and there are various ways to do so. For example, you can do pre- and post-training assessments and measure the improvement; you can then translate this into financial return when you calculate the value of saved time, increased productivity, increased sales. It is important for organizations to view training and development as an investment, not an expense, and to leverage training and development for the achievement of business/organizational goals. Investment in employee training and development should be regarded as a capital investment where you will look for ROI.

3.3. Increased Employee Satisfaction and Retention

Investing in employees training and development enables employees feel more connected, valued, accountable, focused, and part of the team. And while we cannot expect any employee to stay with an organization for their entire career - nor do we necessarily want them to - it has been proven to increase employees' sense of loyalty and decrease turnover. Most people, by nature, want to learn new things, expand their knowledge base and skills set, and grow as professionals. Most people do want to be able to advance in their careers. When the organization has invested in their development, both the company and the individual can reap great rewards. Not only can training and development is a tool for filling knowledge and skills gaps, but also a mechanism for rewarding employees who are high-potentials, high-achievers.

The sub text of all training and development - particularly in-house (custom) programs - is always teambuilding. These initiatives tend to bring employees closer together, strengthen culture, and help individual team members identify new partners, collaborators, mentors and subject-matter experts within the organization (Richard, 2007).

3.4. Nurturing Organizational Learning Culture

It is important to foster a learning culture at your organization, one where expectations are clearly set from the outset, and where the benefits for the employee and for the organization are shared. It is also important to be able to point to success stories within the organization, and to always walk the talk.

In order to ensure their success, it is important to have a plan in place for the transfer of knowledge back at the workplace. You can encourage the employee to implement the key things

they learned right away, and you can create common language and frameworks across your organization by ensuring there is consistency in your training and development approach.

By sending your employees to open enrolment (public) programs where they can network with their peers at different organizations and across industries, they are provided with the forum to test ideas in a safe environment and discuss ideas and best practices that they can bring back to their organization. They should be encouraged to apply these new ideas to their own workplace immediately, and also to share ideas with their teams back at the organization. One way of doing this is to encourage the employee to host a “lunch and learn”, where they can present the key take-aways to their teammates. This will also help with the transfer of knowledge, as it will help to reinforce a culture of learning and create common language and frameworks for the team.

At the end of the day, it is our employees that are our greatest assets. While we upgrade our plant and equipment, we need to renew individual skills sets, upgrade our teams, and arm them with what they need to know to remain competitive and do their best work. In this increasingly competitive global marketplace, the organizations who invest in employee training and development are the ones who will win.

4. Challenges Affecting Training and Development

Training and development is a challenge as many organizations find it difficult to manage their employee. Appointing a training supervisor/director and forgetting him makes training very difficult which may hinder organizational goal few if any have had a substantial training in him to teach and organize a programme for teaching and to evaluate the outcome of training and development. Some training problems emerge when

It is regarded as an end rather than a means to an end, failure of management to accept responsibility for employee training and development, Lack of knowledge and skill by managers in directing and executing training and development, Lack of information concerning the nature of the training process required, If training sees no reason of learning and mastering his assignment and no provision is made for job advancement and benefits and when there is little or no incentive to learn the job ahead. The attitudes of top management staff are crucial to the success of a training and development programme and could make training when their responsibilities are neglected.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

In order to improve employee training and development and improved performance and service delivery, management should increase the number of employees taking part in training and development. This can be done by providing incentives that may motivate employees to take part in training and development programs.

Incentives that could motivate employees to take part in training and development include prospect of promotion or the provision of clear hierarchies in the organization so as to indicate where performance is rewarded.

The possibility of a salary increase can also be used as a motivating factor to encourage employees to take part in employee training and development programs.

It is necessary for companies who are contention for a fair market presence and competition to offer employee training and development programs to their personnel as it will helps in the business profit margins as well as customer satisfaction.

Access to transfer of information on employee training and development programs can be improved by the responsible authorities. This is important in relation to employee training and development as employees can only take part in employee training and development programs when they have access to information about them.

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